

RESULTS OF DETERMINATION OF LABORATORY AND FIELD GERMINATION OF SEEDS OF VEGETABLE BEANS

M.E. Amanova¹, A.P. Khasanov², H.Kh. Khudoyorova³, Z.A. Aktamqulova⁴

Tashkent State Agrarian University, Professor of the Department of Vegetable Growing and Greenhouse Management¹

Tashkent State Agrarian University, Doctoral Student of the Department of Vegetable Growing and Greenhouse Management²

Tashkent State Agrarian University, Assistant of the Department of Vegetable Growing and Greenhouse Management³

Tashkent State Agrarian University, 2nd-year student of the Faculty of Fruit and Vegetable Growing and Viticulture⁴

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Abstract. A three-year (2022–2024) study of 23 bean accessions has been completed. These studies examined the laboratory and field germination of seeds of varieties and accessions of beans. Laboratory germination was determined in 4-fold replication (50 seeds were sown in each replication) in a thermostat at a temperature of +20°C. Seed germination was determined after 8 days, and germination strength was determined after 4 days. To determine field germination, seeds were sown in 4-fold replication (50 seeds per replication) on a 70x15 cm plot to a depth of 4-5 cm. The difference between laboratory and field germination of collection bean accessions was 3,7–19,7%.

Keywords: collection samples of beans, seeds, laboratory and field germination, germination strength.

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations, by 2050, the world population will reach nearly 10 billion people, requiring food production to increase by up to 60% compared to the current period. The rising cost of meat and meat products has further increased the demand for protein-rich crops, including vegetable beans. This is because vegetable beans, in canned, frozen, and dried forms, can be stored for long periods and are considered a strategically important crop. The bean husk possesses antibiotic, dermatonic, and hypoglycemic properties and is widely used in the treatment of hypertension, chronic dermatoses, kidney inflammation, rheumatism, edema, and mild diabetes. In traditional medicine, bean husks are commonly used for their cleansing effects on the body, their ability to regulate blood sugar levels, and their role as a biologically active supplement that revitalizes the body.

Over the past 30 years, several new varieties of leguminous crops, including vegetable beans, have been introduced. In 2022, a total of 330.5 thousand hectares of leguminous crops were cultivated in our country, of which 35.8 thousand hectares were allocated for vegetable beans. Specifically, 5.1 thousand hectares were grown as a primary crop, 24.6 thousand hectares were planted after grain crops, and 6.1 thousand hectares were cultivated in orchard inter-rows.

Our research was conducted on 22 vegetable bean varieties collected during a scientific expedition across Central Asia in collaboration with South Korean scientists and introduced from Turkey. As a standard, we used the *Mahsuldor* variety, which is regionally adapted in our country.

The seed quality indicators of 23 vegetable bean varieties involved in the study were examined under laboratory and field conditions.

In our research, we used high-quality, thoroughly selected seeds of vegetable beans, cultivated using advanced agricultural technologies as a primary crop in 2021. The research was conducted in four replications, with 50 seeds sown per replication. In laboratory conditions, the germination rate of vegetable bean seeds was determined in a thermostat at 20°C within 8 days, while their germination power was assessed within 4 days. In field conditions, seeds were sown on June 1. Before sowing, the field was irrigated and cleared of weeds. The research was conducted in four replications, with 50 seeds sown per replication at a depth of 4-5 cm, with a spacing of 70x15 cm.

Determining the laboratory and field germination of vegetable bean seeds allows for the correct establishment of the seeding rate, preventing excessive seed consumption or a decrease in plant density, which could ultimately reduce yield.

In our research, the *Mahsuldor* variety of vegetable beans was used as the standard. Seed germination was determined on the 6th day after placing the seeds in a thermostat. The laboratory germination rate of the *Mahsuldor* variety was found to be 98%, while the *Qora Shahzoda 01*, *Qizil Shapkacha*, and *Oq Gigant* samples showed a germination rate of 99%. The lowest germination rates, at 95%, were observed in the *Qora Gigant*, *Cezar*, *Olmos*, *Chig'anoq*, and *Turkey Qizil Mayda* samples (Table 1).

The germination rate of the *Korolevskiy*, *Jigar Rang*, *Shahika*, and *Qaldirgoch* vegetable bean varieties was 98%. The *Nigeryanka*, *Kyrgyzstan Qora*, *Zolushka*, *Prusadebnoy*, and *Tomatnaya* varieties had a germination rate of 97%. Meanwhile, the *Jigar Rang Targ'il*, *Kyrgyzstan Qizil*, *Qora Shahzoda 0.2*, and *Rovot* varieties showed a germination rate of 96%.

The vegetable bean samples with the highest germination rates are shown in the following graph (Figure 1).

Table 1. Laboratory Germination of Vegetable Bean Collection Samples

N	Name of plant	The number of sown seeds, pieces.	Replications and the number of germinated seeds, pieces.				Total number of germinated seeds, pieces.	%
			I.	II.	III.	IV.		
			50	50	50	50		
1	Productive (ct).	200	48	50	49	49	196	98
2	Ravot	200	47	49	48	48	192	96
3	Korolevsky	200	49	50	48	49	196	98
4	Black Prince 0.1	200	50	50	49	49	198	99
5	Nigeritanka	200	48	50	48	48	194	97
6	Red Riding Hood	200	49	50	50	49	198	99
7	Liver-colored speckled	200	49	49	48	50	196	96
8	Black Giant	200	47	49	46	48	190	95
9	Kyrgyzstan Black	200	47	49	48	50	194	97
10	Kyrgyzstan Red	200	49	48	47	48	192	96
11	Brown	200	49	48	49	50	196	98
12	Zolushka	200	47	49	49	49	194	97
13	Caesar	200	49	46	47	48	190	95
14	White Giant	200	50	49	50	49	198	99
15	Shahika	200	49	49	49	49	196	98
16	Almos	200	46	47	48	49	190	95
17	Kaldirgach	200	50	48	49	49	196	98
18	Priusadebnoy	200	48	48	48	50	194	97
19	Tomato	200	50	48	47	49	194	97
20	Chiganoch	200	47	48	47	48	190	95
21	Black Prince 0.2	200	49	48	47	48	192	96
22	Turkey Small Red	200	47	48	47	48	190	95
23	Tablet	200	49	49	48	50	196	98

In field conditions, the vegetable bean seeds were soaked for 6 hours before planting in typical gray soils at a depth of 4–5 cm. On June 6, 10% of the seeds had germinated, and by June 10, the germination rate reached 75%.

The highest field germination rates were observed in the *Kizil Shapochka* (Russia), *Qora Shahzoda*, and *Jigar Rang* (Kyrgyzstan) samples, with germination rates of 95.5%–94.7%. In contrast, the lowest results were recorded for the *Zolushka* (77.3%), *Qora Gigant* (85.6%), and *Jigar Rang Targ'il* (86.4%) samples.

The remaining varieties and samples showed intermediate results.

According to the research results, the highest field germination rates were recorded in the *Kizil Shapochka* (95.5%), *Qora Shahzoda 01* (94.7%), *Jigar Rang* (94.7%), and *Qaldirgoch* (94.7%) varieties. These rates were found to be 1.5%–2.3% higher than those of the standard variety (Table 2).

Figure 1. Vegetable Bean Collection Samples with High Laboratory Germination Rates

Table 2. Field Germination Rates of Vegetable Bean Varieties and Samples

N	Name of Plant	Planted seeds, amount	I repeat.	II repeat.	III repeat.	IV repeat.	Avg. number of seedlings	Seed germination %
			Seedlings	Seedlings	Seedlings	Seedlings		
			Number	Number	Number	Number		
1	Productive (ct).	200	47	46	46	47	46,5	93,2
2	Ravot	200	48	43	47	48	46,5	93,2
3	Korolevsky	200	45	49	46	48	47	93,9
4	Black Prince 0.1	200	48	46	49	47	47,5	94,7
5	Nigeritanka	200	46	48	47	43	46	91,7
6	Red Riding Hood	200	49	47	48	47	47,75	95,5
7	Liver-colored speckled	200	44	45	41	43	43,25	86,4
8	Black Giant	200	47	43	39	42	42,75	85,6
9	Kyrgyzstan Black	200	47	45	44	46	45,50	90,9
10	Kyrgyzstan Red	200	45	46	48	47	46,50	93,2
11	Brown	200	46	48	49	47	47,5	94,7

12	Zolushka	200	41	39	35	40	38,75	77,3
13	Caesar	200	46	48	47	44	46,25	92,4
14	White Giant	200	46	44	47	48	46,25	92,4
15	Shahika	200	47	45	47	46	46,25	92,4
16	Almos	200	46	47	46	49	47,00	93,9
17	Kaldirgach	200	46	48	49	47	47,50	94,7
18	Priusadebnoy	200	44	47	43	45	44,75	92,4
19	Tomato	200	49	46	47	46	47	93,9
20	Chiganoch	200	44	46	45	47	45,5	90,9
21	Black Prince 0.2	200	46	49	46	43	46,00	91,7
22	Turkey Small Red	200	45	47	46	48	46,50	93,2
23	Tablet	200	44	47	49	48	47,00	93,9

The lowest field germination rates were recorded in the *Zolushka*, *Qora Gigant*, and *Jigar Rang Targ'il* samples, showing a decrease of 6.8%–15.5% compared to the standard *Mahsuldor* variety (*Graph 2*).

During the research process, it was determined that there is an inverse correlation between seed germination speed and seed weight. The larger the seed is, the longer its water absorption process is, leading to a relatively delayed germination.

Graph 2. Field Germination Rates of Vegetable Bean Varieties and Samples

It can be observed that seeds with high germination rates in laboratory conditions do not always exhibit similarly high germination rates in field conditions (*Graph 3*). For example, the *Oq Gigant* sample had a laboratory germination rate of 99%, but its field germination rate was 92.4%. Similarly, the *Qizil Shapkacha* variety showed a laboratory germination rate of 99%.

Graph 3. Agrobiological Characteristics of Vegetable Bean Variety Seeds

The field germination rate was 95.5%, with differences of 3.5–6.6%, respectively. Conversely, the *Ravot* variety, which had a laboratory germination rate of 96%, exhibited a field germination rate of 93.2%.

It can be observed from *Graph 3* that the difference between laboratory and field germination rates for vegetable bean collection samples ranged from 3.7% to 19.7%.

Conclusion

1. The field germination rate and emergence speed of vegetable bean seeds are strongly influenced by storage methods, seed structure, seed size, temperature, soil moisture, and planting depth.
2. Since the field germination rate is lower than the laboratory germination rate, it is recommended to increase the seeding rate accordingly.

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